

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Tomila Lankina (2018): Lankina Russian Protest-Event Dataset (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/671E83A6-0492-4A3B-8DF7-659405441349>

Abstract

The Lankina Russian protest event dataset (LaruPED) is a project by Tomila Lankina that covers a wide range of protests across Russia in the time period from March 2007 to December 2016. It defines a protest as: “Citizens’ public expression of dissent or critique” (Lankina 2019) and is thus not imposing a necessary number of participants as a prerequisite for a protest to be included in this dataset. The unit of analysis in the LaruPED dataset is the event-day-location, meaning events that occur in multiple locations are coded as separate entries. In total the dataset contains 5.824 coded protests (Lankina 2019). As of summer 2024, it is unclear whether work on the data collection is continuing. The data review includes a link to the LSE Research Online website from which the dataset, as well as additional information about the dataset in the form of a codebook and a descriptive text, is available for download.

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Data Review – Lankina Russian Protest-Event Dataset

The Lankina Russian protest event dataset (LArUPED) is a project by Tomila Lankina that covers a wide range of protests across Russia in the timespan from March 2007 to December 2016. It defines a protest as: “Citizens’ public expression of dissent or critique” (Lankina 2019) and is thus not imposing a necessary number of participants as a prerequisite for a protest to be included in this dataset. The unit of analysis in the LArUPED dataset is the event-day-location, meaning events that occur in multiple locations are coded as separate entries. In total the dataset contains 5.824 coded protests (Lankina 2019). As of summer 2024, it is unclear whether work on the data collection is continuing.

The LArUPED dataset compiles its information by utilizing the “Novosti protesta” (Protest News Section) of the namarsh.ru website. This website harvested protest news from different sources across Russia. These sources include: A network of regional correspondents, press and online reports, other online websites (e.g. kasparov.ru), as well as social media (Lankina 2019).

During the coding process, which was conducted exclusively by human coders, identifying relevant protests was the first step. During this, all stories that only mentioned intentions to mobilize, other forms of political participation such as petitions or stories about citizens’ general discontent were disregarded. Neither does the dataset include events organized by the ruling United Russia party, or pro-government youth movements such as Nashi. After manually filtering the entries on the website, approximately 66% of all reported stories were included in the dataset (Lankina 2019). The next step was the manual extraction of relevant information from these stories. Here, the research team focused on the following variables: the date the protest occurred, its duration and location, the number of participants as well as the number of those getting apprehended. On top of that, the dataset categorizes the type of event that occurs on whether it is a demonstration, march, strike, other symbolic act, hunger strike, railway block, road block, occupation, suicide or other disruptive act. Besides the typical political protests (2.382 entries), the dataset also lists economic (1.048 entries), social (1.328 entries), cultural (155 entries), environmental (550 entries), and legal (801 entries) protests. For an easier overview of the data, the research team introduced the “civic” and “civic+” categories which are aggregate categories that include any protest that are registered as legal, cultural and environmental (civic) or legal, cultural, environmental and social (civic+) respectively. Furthermore, the dataset includes information on whether suppression occurred either during the protests, or if protests were thwarted before they could take place (Lankina 2019; (2)).

Lastly, all entries within the dataset contain a link to the original news article from which the information was extracted. This is especially relevant since information on some variables is only available from 2012-2013 onward, so users can refer to these original sources to extract the missing information themselves (Lankina 2019; (2)). These links however, are no longer

active because the namarsh.ru website has since been taken down. Namarsh.ru can however still be accessed by utilizing the wayback machine (https://web.archive.org/web/20230101000000*/http://namarsh.ru/). There the data is still accessible up to the latest snapshot on the 12th of April 2023.

As indicated above the LARuPED dataset is very broad in its thematic scope and can thus be utilized for a number of different analyses. The research team however, highlights its utility in being used to document important differences in the type of violently suppressed protests. One such use, would be using the dataset to analyze the likelihood of political protests being violently suppressed by the Russian government (30%) compared to those protests classified as civic (21%) (Lankina 2019).

On the other hand, limitations of the dataset include the reliance on only one platform as a source for information. Thus, it is possible that certain regions or events might be under-reported/over-reported based on the bias of the website. Since namarsh.ru has been funded by Garry Kasparov, an opposition politician, it might contain a bias towards pro-democracy activism (for a detailed analysis of this issue please refer to Dollbaum's "Protest Event Analysis Under Conditions of Limited Press Freedom: Comparing Data Sources."). Worth mentioning is also that 35% of the entries listed on the website do not report the number of protest participants, meaning that this information is also missing from the dataset (Lankina 2019).

The research team tried to cross-validate the existing data with additional protest archives, mainly using the website of the Institute of Collective Action (IKD) for the period from December 2011 to May 2012, while only covering political protests. During this research 90 additional events were identified that were not included on the namarsh.ru website. Thus, the research team states the following: "It is [...] important to note that LARuPED does not provide an exhaustive account of protest events. We are explicit about these limitations and highlight that the data should be regarded as complementary to other data sources [...], and not as an exclusive and comprehensive repository of information on protests in Russia." (Lankina 2019).

Note: Next to the dataset and the codebook which are available from the LSE Research Online website, a third document (Text: Memo to users) is also available for download. This document includes a web address that is no longer active and instead produces a virus warning.

Sources:

- (1) Lankina, T., & Tertychnaya, K. (2019). Protest in electoral autocracies: a new dataset. *Post-Soviet Affairs*, 36(1), 20–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1060586X.2019.1656039>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (2) Russian protest data codebook. 2018. Available for download here: <http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/90298/>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.